

SOME SPECIFIC FEATURES OF TEACHING IDIOMS IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN THE SECONDARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

A phrase or expression that typically conveys a figurative rather than literal meaning is known as an idiom. However, there are some phrases that retain their literal meaning but become figurative idioms. Sorted as standard language, a phrase's non-literal significance is not the same as the exacting importance. Idioms are cultural and social phenomena that refer to communicative human behavior and reflect social mental characteristics of behavior. They suggest communication standards, rules, and conventions for this or that lingua-cultural community. It is common knowledge in linguistics that subjective implications accompany informal expressions.

The article discusses some ways of teaching idioms to learners. Some topical expressions and their meanings in Russian language are given. There can be seen the main features of some exercises which are helpful for improving speech and pupils' knowledge.

Key words: *a foreign language, fiction, newspapers, magazines, television programs, idiomatic expressions, exercises.*

INTRODUCTION

In order to speak a foreign language as a native speaker, you need to know, be able to understand and use set expressions or idioms. English, in terms of the presence in its extensive system of idiomatic expressions, is perhaps one of the richest. Idioms occupy a huge layer in its structure. They can be heard in daily conversations, friendly conversations, discussions, business meetings. They can also be found in fiction, newspapers, magazines, television programs. Idioms give the language a bright color, make it more lively, emotional and informal. By definition, an idiom is a phrase consisting of two or more words, the meaning of which is not determined by the meaning of its constituent words. Obviously, an English idiom is a turn of speech that is not transmitted verbatim into Russian. Therefore, it must be remembered.

METHODOLOGY

In 1970 Fraser paid a special attention to multi-word expressions that are syntactically complex and fixed to some degree typically receive in the study of language. In the Anglo-Saxon culture, these expressions are typically referred to by the term idiom. These theories had been studied by Fillmore, Kay, and O'Connor during 1970 and 1988. In the sense that they are multi-word units that are fixed to some extent, either in form (that is, in their morpho-syntactic properties) or in meaning (considering that it cannot be built by regular principles of grammar), these terms gather expressions that correspond in some way to formulaic language. It has been determined whether their idiomaticity is contained in the lexicon or outside of grammar. These had been studied by Katz & Postal in [1963](#). The great linguistics like Flaster, Chomskiy, Mueller and Gibbs, Nenonen, Niemi, Laine, Lakoff, Johnson, Gibbs also studied the main features of idioms and phraseological units.

RESULTS

Idiomatic expressions in English are an interesting and at the same time difficult topic to study. English idioms are very specific, and their literal translation into their native language is simply impossible, as it distorts the meaning to the point of complete misunderstanding. For example, the idiom "go Dutch" can be understood as, "go, act like Dutch," but in fact it means "to pay a fortune." Therefore, you should not make the so-called "tracing paper" from the Russian language. Sometimes idioms are surprisingly similar to their Russian counterparts. For example, the idiom "look for a needle in a bottom of hay" literally translates as "look for a needle in a haystack" and has the same meaning, and we understand its meaning.

Student needs to know the following items in order to learn idioms successfully:

- 1) the order of words in idioms does not change;
- 2) they are not translated verbatim into their native language;
- 3) idioms are used only in a figurative sense;
- 4) they can only be memorized;

5) the use of idioms indicates a high knowledge of the language, since they make speech more natural.

In schools, the study of idioms is given special attention, since idioms are a bright and nationally unique part of the language picture of the world. Studying idiomatic expressions, students simultaneously penetrate into a new national culture that reflects the centuries-old history of the people, get acquainted with the peculiarities of the English language, acquire great spiritual wealth that has been accumulated over the years and preserved in the language. With the help of idioms that require rethinking,

the informational aspect of the language is supplemented by a sensory-intuitive, that is, aesthetic aspect, and speech becomes more multifaceted. In addition, idioms contribute to the development of functional literacy, develop a linguistic guess, and encourage discussion based on the meaning of one or another idiomatic phrase. In English lessons, idioms are studied thematically. Almost every module, it can be found the most commonly used English idioms that correspond to the subject of the module.

In Uzbekistan starting from the 8th grade, working with idioms in the classroom becomes regular. Since a feature of the general education program implemented in our gymnasium is an expanded humanitarian component, additional hours are allocated for the study of a foreign language, during which the study of various language aspects is expanded, including the study of idioms that are not included in the lesson material on this topic. Additional idioms are selected by the teacher, who also composes exercises for working out the material covered, as well as test tasks. When practicing idioms, in addition to the exercises from the textbook and workbook, I use the following exercises. This is a presentation lesson on a given topic; make up dialogues with the replacement of these expressions with idiomatic ones; explain the meaning of idioms in English; working in groups, find as many idioms and phrasal verbs as possible in the given text; write a letter to a friend using learned idioms; find the correct answer (multiple choice exercises); working in a team, remember as many English idioms as possible, the meaning of which coincides with Russian idioms; make up an idiom on a given topic from these letters; written tasks - reasoning that involves the disclosure and transmission of the meaning of a particular idiom; insert the correct word into the idiom; Write a test based on what you have learned. Thus, it is obvious that the study of idioms contributes to a more intensive assimilation of lexical material and develops students' reading, writing and speaking skills, depending on the proposed exercises. The study and correct use of idioms is of great interest to students. Therefore, by the end of the gymnasium, in addition to excellent pronunciation and confident knowledge of English grammar, our graduates have a large stock of idiomatic expressions, which facilitates their communication with native speakers of a foreign language, and also relieves difficulties when reading fiction in the original. So, We would like to highlight several groups of thematic idioms.

Idioms on body parts:

A pain in the neck – зануда, невыносимый человек

Get off one's back – отстать, оставить в покое

Give someone the cold shoulder – оказывать холодный прием

Like a bear with a sore head – разъяренный, разозленный

See eye to eye – сходиться во взглядах с кем-либо

Be a pain in the neck – создавать проблемы

Hold one's tongue – держать язык за зубами

Make somebody's hair stand on end – сильно напугать кого-либо

Keep one's fingers crossed – желать ни пуха, ни пера

Pull someone's leg – дразнить, подшучивать над кем-либо

Lose one's head – паниковать, впадать в панику, терять голову

Give someone a hand – помогать

Put one's foot down – приказать или запретить что-либо делать

Sweet tooth – сладкоежка

Eye-catching – заметный

All ears – быть в предвкушении подробного рассказа о чем-то

Break someone's heart = разбить сердце

After teaching idiomatic expressions some exercises for consolidation will be done. The following tasks may be given in order to strengthen pupils' knowledge.

They are the followings:

I. Correct the mistakes

1. Steve would not take to James after their argument. He has given him the cold hand.

2. We bought Kate a box of chocolates for her birthday. She has such a sweet tongue!

3. Did you see Ann in her new dress? She is very face-catching!

4. If you want me to hear you out, I am all eyes!

5. Keep your arms crossed for me tomorrow - it's my job interview.

6. She broke his mind when she left him.

7. He always gives me a head with the housework.

8. The film was so scary it made my nails stand on end.

9. Of course I won't tell Mum. I was only pulling your neck.

Answers can be the followings: 1.shoulder, 2.tooth, 3.eye, 4.ears, 5.fingers, 6.heart, 7.hand, 8.hair, 9.Leg

II. Fill in the blanks with the correct words.(foot, back, eye, neck, head).

1. Julia wanted to go to the party but her farther put his down.

2. They never agree with each other. They don't see eye to

3. What's wrong with him? He's like a bear with a sore

4. My brother talks too much. He's a real pain in the

5. She is so bossy. Why doesn't she get off my ?

Answers: 1.foot, 2.eye, 3.head, 4.neck, 5.back.

Idioms about food and cooking. A lot of English idioms are related to the topic of food.

Apple of one's eye – чей-то любимчик, “зеница ока”

As cool as a cucumber – абсолютно спокойный

Be a piece of cake – что-то простое, элементарное

Bread and butter – средства к существованию.

Couch potato - лежебока

Cry over spilt milk – сожалеть о непоправимом

Full of beans – полон энергии

Have your cake and eat it – пытаться совместить несовместимое

In hot water – в заботах, хлопотах

It's not my cup of tea – это не по мне

Make one's mouth water – слюнки текут

Sell like hot cakes – идти на ура, расходятся как горячие пирожки

Spill the beans – раскрыть карты, разболтать секрет

Take something with a pinch of salt – не принимать в серьез

Take the cake – отвратительно вести себя

The icing on the cake – самый лучший

Use your noodle – шевели мозгами

Now we will give some tasks in order to test pupils' knowledge.

1. I'm sorry that you broke your bicycle, but it's no use crying over spilt

a) tea b) cream c) milk d) wine

2. Solving math problems is a piece of ... for him.

a) pie b) bread c) cake d) pizza

3. Opera isn't exactly my

a) glass of juice b) mug of coffee c) jar of honey d) cup of tea

4. After the sleep, I was again full of ...

a) peas b) soup c) beans d) pasta

5. This task is not as difficult as it seems. Just use your ...

a) Google b) noodle c) phone d) computer

6. Baby Helen is the ... of her mother's eye.

a) pear b) cherry c) lemon d) apple

7. During the fire the homeowner was cool as a

a) tomato b) mineral water c) ice-cream d) cucumber

8. Ann loves telling stories, so take everything she says with a pinch of

a) pepper b) salt c) garlic d) onion

9. Teaching is my bread and

a) cheese b) salt c) butter d) mustard

10. She is a real couch ...! She is fond of lying on the couch watching TV!

a) potato b) tomato c) cucumber d) cabbage

11. This cafe is really nice and every time that I see the menu it makes my ...

water.

a) tongue b) mouth c) eyes d) neck

12. Please don't spill the ... and tell the secret to anyone.

a) cherries b) milk c) apples d) beans

13. His new novel sells like hot

a) soup b) chocolate c) coffee d) cakes

Answers: 1.milk 2.cake 3. cup of tea 4.beans 5.noodle 6.apple 7.cucumber 8.salt
9. butter 10.potato 11.mouth 12.beans 13.cakes.

Weather idioms. For the British, the topic of weather is very important. In the UK people talk about the weather all the time as it changes all the time. Residents of the country usually start a conversation with friends or strangers about the weather. This topic is neutral. Therefore, on the street you can often hear such words: "What a lovely day!" or "It looks like it will be raining the whole day". Perhaps because of this attention to the weather, there are a lot of idioms about the weather in the English language.

A face like thunder – темнее тучи

A storm in a teacup – буря в стакане воды

As right as rain – в полном порядке

Be on cloud nine - быть очень счастливым по какому-нибудь поводу

Be a bolt from the blue – быть неожиданной новостью

Break the ice - сказать или сделать что-то, чтобы снять напряжение

Come rain or shine – во что бы то ни стало, при любой ситуации

Every cloud has a silver lining – нет худа без добра

Feel under the weather - плохо себя чувствовать, быть в плохом настроении

For a rainy day - на черный день

Head in the clouds – витать в облаках, предаваться бесплодным фантазиям

It never rains but it pours – беда не приходит одна

Raining cats and dogs – льет как из ведра

Storm in a teacup – буря в стакане воды

Save up for a rainy day – копить деньги на черный день

See which way the wind blows – знать откуда ветер дует, быть в курсе

The calm before the storm – затишье перед бурей

To twist in the wind – томиться

To feel under the weather – плохо себя чувствовать

To throw caution to the wind – перестать осторожничать

To weather the storm - пережить трудные времена

For weather idioms the following tasks can be given so that to strengthen pupils' knowledge:

Correct the mistakes.

1. Come shine or rain I'll be at the meeting tomorrow.
 2. It always snows and it pours – today I have lost my purse and then a job.
 3. They were on cloud seven after the birth of their son.
 4. We are going to have much work tomorrow. So now is the sun before the storm.
 5. We are not having vacation this year, but every cloud has a silver chain. We are going to save money.
 6. She offered to have a cup of coffee to break the snow.
 7. It was raining dogs and cats all the weekend so we decided to stay at home.
 8. The new law caused a rain in a teacup – it's really not that strict.
 9. If you think you'll pass your exams without any revising, you have your head in the water.
 10. Anna was feeling a little under the ocean that day so she cancelled the date.
 11. When he's angry, he's got a voice like thunder!
 12. He wasn't expecting it to happen. It was a thunder out of the blue.
 13. Don't spend your money. It's wise to save up for the cold day.
- Answers: 1.rain or shine 2. never rains but 3.nine 4.calm 5.lining 6.ice 7.cats and dogs 8.storm 9.clouds 10. weather 11. face 12.storm 13.rainy

Idioms about animals. The love for cats, dogs and horses is a well-known British passion, so many original English idioms are related to animals.

Bark up the wrong tree – идти по ложному следу

Take the bull by the horns – взять быка за рога

Have a bee in one's bonnet – помешать сума чем-либо

Butterflies in one's stomach - мандраж, «мурашки бегают», ни жив ни мертв

Not enough room to swing a cat – очень мало места, чтобы жить комфортно

Can talk the hind legs off a donkey - человек, который много говорит

Straight from the horse's mouth – получить информацию напрямую

Take under someone's wing – взять под крыло

Be like water off a duck's back - что-то, что не имеет никакого эффекта

Not to have a cat in hell's chance - совсем не иметь возможности что-то сделать

Put a cat among the pigeons - сделать или сказать что-то, что принесет проблемы и заставит много людей волноваться

Curiosity killed the cat - любопытство может причинить проблемы

Be like a red rag to a bull – как красная тряпка быку

Pussy foot around - ходить вокруг да около

Let the cat out of the bag - открыть секрет или случайно рассказать о сюрпризе

Monkey see, monkey do – обезьянничать; дурные примеры заразительны.

The following task can be given as an example.

Match the idioms with the suitable definitions.

1. Not enough room to swing a cat	a) make someone very angry
2. Can talk the hind legs off a donkey	b) help and protect someone, especially someone who is younger than you or has less experience than you
3. Straight from the horse’s mouth	c) have no chance at all of doing something
4. Take under someone’s wing	d) go about timidly and cautiously
5. Be like water off a duck’s back	e) do or say something that causes trouble and makes a lot of people angry or worried
6. Not to have a cat in hell’s chance	f) a room is very small and there is not enough space to live comfortably in it
7. Put a cat among the pigeons	g) information directly from someone who knows it
8. Curiosity killed the cat	h) a person who can talk a lot
9. Be like a red rag to a bull	i) reveal a secret or a surprise by accident
10. Pussy foot around	k) Being curious can get you into trouble
11. Let the cat out of the bag	l) it has no effect on someone at all (usually criticism)

Answers: 1.f 2.h 3.g 4.b 5.l 6.c 7.e 8.k 9.a 10.d 11.i

DISCUSSION

Many native English speakers use idioms, informal colloquial expressions, and slang, especially when conversing among themselves. As a result, finding authentic examples to explain what idioms mean and how they are used in real life can be a challenge when teaching idioms. Video clips from TV shows, interviews, and even songs can be a great resource for teaching idioms in context. Play the clips and conduct a gap-fill activity to listen for idioms, or conduct a matching activity in which students listen and use what they hear to match the idioms with the definitions. You can even incorporate these clips into a game. Please see the following section of the article for game suggestions. While these resources are widely available on the Internet,

compiling them may take some time. Take some time before teaching your list to prepare your online resources and save them for later use. Another method for obtaining authentic examples is to have students search newspapers or even magazines. This activity idea is ideal for first-time idiom introduction to students. Depending on your students' level, choose articles with examples of idioms and have them go on a "treasure hunt." Students can search for the idioms on your list in pairs or small groups. You can use the meanings as hints to help them complete the task. You can project or write the clues on the board, or you can give them a separate worksheet to help them find the idioms in the text.

If you have access to resources such as electronic devices or a computer lab, you can put your students to work by asking them to look up the definition and examples of their use. Make a list of idioms and challenge students to find meanings for the idioms you're teaching that day. Another option is to assign 2-3 idioms to a pair of students and have them teach the meanings of each idiom to the class after some research. Several studies have found that the more time and effort students put into actively learning something, the more they retain.

CONCLUSION

The use of idioms demonstrates that the English language is dynamic and constantly changing. Some idioms may be considered archaic, depending on the context, while others are current and relevant. Idioms can be used as teachable moments in the classroom, such as discussing which expressions are currently or frequently used by speakers in the country where we are teaching. Idioms can also be used to demonstrate how metaphorical and creative the English language can be. Use any of the methods listed above to include a few idioms as part of a mini-lesson or as an engaging activity to help your students develop a more diverse vocabulary and a more flexible range and use of the English language.

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